

Information Management in Schools in the Digital Age

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Abstract

Effective information management is critical to the smooth operation and academic success of schools in the digital age. This paper explores the strategies, systems, and tools used to collect, store, manage, and disseminate information within educational institutions. It examines how schools can leverage information management systems (IMS) to enhance administrative efficiency, support data-driven decision-making, and improve communication among stakeholders including administrators, teachers, students, and parents. The study also considers the challenges schools face in implementing these systems, such as data privacy concerns, digital literacy gaps, and financial constraints. By analyzing case studies and best practices, this research highlights the importance of adopting integrated and secure information management solutions to foster a more organized, transparent, and responsive educational environment.

Keywords: *Information system, Technology Acceptance Model, perceived usefulness.*

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Introduction

Information management in schools refers to the systematic handling of information resources to enhance educational processes, decision-making, and administrative efficiency. With the growing reliance on technology and data in education, effective information management has become crucial for schools to improve learning outcomes and streamline operations. This work was based on specific acceptance models and theories of social psychology regarding the factors that influence the use of technology and various information systems. These are the Technology Acceptance Model and the Information System Success Model (Information System (IS) success model).

Theoretical Models of Technology Acceptance and Use

In the literature review, there are several theories and models concerning the acceptance and use of technology or various information systems. The first model is the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) of Davis (1989), which was later developed into TAM2 (Venkatesh, & Davis, 2000) and TAM3 (Venkatesh, & Bala, 2008). Important theories that preceded or followed TAM are the Theory of Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) of Rogers (1995) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) of Venkatesh et al. (2003). In parallel with these theories, the Information System Success Model (Information System (IS) success model) (DeLone, & McLean, 1992, DeLone, & McLean, 2003). In relation to the above models, this research utilized the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as well as the Information System Success Model (Information System (IS) success model). The reasons for this choice of these two models are: 1) Both models refer more to the acceptance of information

systems compared to the other models which refer to simple applications of Information and Communication Technologies. The “MySchool” is considered an information system and therefore the two specific theories are considered more suitable for it. 2) Both TAM and the Information System Success Model have variables that are more suitable for samples of teachers and principals, as in the present study. These variables are closer to the profile of principals and therefore can be better evaluated by them compared to other models. These variables are related, among other things, to the ease and usefulness of “MySchool”, its quality, and principals’ satisfaction with its use.

Technology Acceptance Model

The Technology Acceptance Model (Technology Acceptance Model), designed by Davis et al. (1989) and is largely based on the Theory of Reasoned Action. The aim of the Technology Acceptance Model is to explain the reasons why users use ICT while others do not. To achieve this, the model relies on specific variables. More specifically, it is assumed that the variables of Perceived Ease of Use (Perceived Ease of Use) and Perceived Usefulness (Perceived Usefulness) influence users' attitudes towards the use of a particular technology and, through intention, essentially the actual use (Davis et al., 1989; Igbaria et al., 1995; Karahanna & Straub, 1999; Smarkola, 2008). In addition, the variables of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness are influenced by various external factors. These factors may include gender, age, knowledge and skills about ICT. The Technology Acceptance Model is presented in Figure 1 and is analyzed in more detail later in the section.

Figure 1. The Technology Acceptance Model

Source: Davis et al., 1989

Actual Use

According to Davis et al. (1989), what we are interested in in the Technology Acceptance Model is the actual use of the technology, that is, whether users will use the specific technology. Whether an individual will use the technology depends largely on intention.

Behavioural Intention to Use

According to the Technology Acceptance Model, the intention to use technology directly depends on the perceived usefulness and attitudes towards the use of technology.

Attitudes towards the Use of Technology

Attitudes towards behavior play an essential role in shaping intention. According to Ajzen (1991), attitudes are the overall evaluation of the effects, positive and negative, that may result from the potential

use of technology. For example, one may have a positive attitude towards the use of an information system if he believes that specific benefits will arise from such use. Conversely, one may have a negative attitude towards the use of an information system if he believes that specific disadvantages will arise from such use. According to the Technology Acceptance Model, attitudes are influenced by the perceived usefulness and convenience of the technology. In other words, if an individual believes that potential benefits will arise from the future use of the technology and, at the same time, thinks that he can handle it with ease, then his attitudes towards the use of the technology become more positive. On the other hand, Ajzen (2006) argues that attitudes are influenced by behavioral beliefs that concern specific advantages and disadvantages that may arise from the potential use of the technology. The definition of perceived usefulness is presented in the next subsection of the chapter.

Perceived Ease of Use

According to Davis et al., (1989), perceived ease of use is defined as the extent to which an individual believes that using a particular technology will be easy, that is, it will not require effort. This variable, as shown in Figure 1, has a direct impact on perceived or perceived usefulness. Several factors are related to this element of the model. Some of them are the ability to use the technology, the ability to control the classroom when using the technology, the adequacy of the user's training, support from colleagues as well as the creation of incentives for using the technology.

Perceived or Perceived Usefulness

Perceived or perceived usefulness, in the Technology Acceptance Model, is defined as the extent to which an individual believes that using a particular technology will improve their performance at work (Davis et al., 1989). Perceived usefulness directly influences the individual's intention to use the technology (see more in: Park et al., 2009). This seems logical, since the greater the usefulness an individual perceives in a technology, the more likely they are to want to use it. Prestone et al., (2000), argue that there are various factors associated with perceived usefulness. These factors for the field of education are related, among other things, to the increase or not of the difficulty of a system, the effect of incentives on engagement with technology as well as the possibility of professional development of teachers and education executives.

External Variables

In the Technology Acceptance Model, external variables play a major role (Davis, 1993). Among these variables, it has been found that the demands of the school curriculum (Kim, 2000), the personal skills of those who handle technology (Hong et al., 2002), the attitudes of students and, more generally, parents and guardians, as well as the wider educational and trade union community, as well as the school's policies regarding the use of ICT (Brummelhuis & Plomp, 1994) play an important role. To the above, the gender and age of the users of their technology as well as their broader attitude towards educational change and innovation (Fullan, 2007) must be added.

The Technology Acceptance Model has been applied either alone or together with other variables in many studies. The majority of these studies showed that the model is quite reliable and they applied it either as is or extended it with other variables, depending on the purpose of their research each time (see, for example, the following studies: Lee, Yoon&Lee, 2009, Islam, 2013, Decman, 2015, Lee, Yoon&Lee, 2009, Lee, Yoon&Lee, 2009, Islam, 2013, Teo, 2011, Lau&Woods, 2009, Sanchez-Franco, Martinez-Lopez&Martin-Velicia, 2009, Ifinedo, 2015, Althunibat, 2015, Nikou&Economides, 2017, Briz-Ponce, Pereira, Carvalho, Juanes-Mendez&García-Penalvo, 2017, Ho, Hung&Chen, 2013, Althunibat, 2015).

Information System (IS) Success Model

The Information System (IS) success model, or the DeLone and McLean Success Model (1992), is a theory that specifically addresses information systems (see Figure 2). The theory was initially developed by William H. DeLone and Ephraim R. McLean in 1992 and further refined by the authors themselves a

decade later (DeLone & McLean, 2003), in response to feedback from other scholars working in the field. The Success Model identifies the relationships between six dimensions of information system service success. These dimensions are system technical quality, information quality, system technical support, system use/intentions to use, user satisfaction, and system benefits. These dimensions are presented in Figure 2 and detailed in the next section.

Figure 2. The Information System Success Model

According to Mamma (2008) the variables of the Success Model of an Information System are defined as follows:

- Technical system quality (System Quality) refers to how good an information system is in terms of its functional characteristics.
- Information Quality refers to how good an information system is in terms of its outputs. In other words, information quality can be related to relevance, accuracy, relevance, completeness, reliability, and content.

Regarding technical support, this is related to all the technical features of the information system and the extent to which there is support for users regarding them. This technical support can be, among other things, live, or seminars, or training, online, via email, forum, video with usage details, frequently asked questions (Mohammadi, 2015).

On the other hand, intention is related to whether a user intends, plans or will attempt to use an information system in the context of their professional development (DeLone & McLean, 2003). System use is related to whether a user uses the information system in their work as well as other parameters related to use such as frequency of use and reasons for it. Finally, and most importantly in the Information System Success Model, is the satisfaction dimension. Satisfaction is related to how users perceive the potential use of the system. In other words, to how satisfied they are with its use or to how much they believe they will be satisfied with the use of the information system.

According to Figure 2, a school principal, in order to use “MySchool” for administrative purposes, beyond the official policy of the Ministry of Education, needs to have positive attitudes towards the dimension of information quality. That is, to believe that the information the system provides is distinguished by reliability, completeness, quality, etc. Also, he must believe that “MySchool” has such

functional features that will be distinguished by quality and usability and therefore will not make it difficult for him to use it. On the other hand, a principal need to have or believe that he will be able to have direct and reliable technical support, for example from the “MySchool” helpdesk. If the principal has positive attitudes towards these three dimensions, then according to DeLone and McLean, (2003) there is a high probability that he will have a strong intention to use the “MySchool” information system. In addition, there is a possibility that he will experience a higher degree of satisfaction. Therefore, a stronger intention and a greater degree of satisfaction may contribute to the use of "MySchool" for the administration and organization of one's school unit.

Figure 3. Combination of Technology Acceptance Model and Information System Success Model

Source: Mohammadi, 2015

Recently, Mohammadi (2015) used the Success Model with the Technology Acceptance Model, discussed above, to investigate students’ perceptions of e-learning. Specifically, Mohammadi added educational quality, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease to the Information System Success Model (see Figure 3). The results of Mohammadi’s study showed that the new model explained students’ satisfaction and intention to use e-learning quite well. More specifically, the results of Mohammadi’s study showed that the variables of intention and satisfaction also had positive effects on the actual use of e-learning. System quality and information quality were found to be the primary factors influencing students’ intentions and satisfaction with the use of e-learning. Furthermore, the variable of perceived usefulness mediated the relationship between perceived ease of use and students' intentions to use e-learning.

Conclusion

In the evolving landscape of education, effective information management is vital for schools striving to enhance learning experiences and operational efficiency. By prioritizing data management practices, schools can harness the power of information to foster a supportive and effective educational environment.

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